

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) – Pre-proposal

Section 1 – Applicant(s)

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Section 2 – Summary

Proposed project title	SPI-Birds Data Entry Software (SPI-BirDES): closing the FAIR data life cycle on the ecology of breeding birds
Project type	Small (type 1)
Project duration	24 months

Section 3 – Project description

3.1 Alignment of your project with the aim of the call

Historical and long-term data are critical for understanding how wildlife respond to our changing world. Globally, data on the breeding ecology of birds are some of the longest and richest time series available. By their very nature, these data are extremely heterogenous; both in their coverage (taxonomic, geographic, and temporal), and management (formats, vocabularies, archiving). This heterogeneity persists despite the fact many studies collect the same basic information (e.g., breeding data like egg laying dates and number of offspring, and morphological measurements like body mass). Such data management diversity poses challenges to the combination and synthesis of data from different ecological contexts, limiting capacity for data reuse and, ultimately, the assessment of the

Figure 1 | our proposed DES in the context of the FAIR data life cycle and existing SPI-Birds infrastructure

generality of ecological mechanisms. Similarly, *ad hoc* and under-resourced data entry and management tools pose serious threats to the quality, integration, and archiving of these irreplaceable data assets. **These issues are mutually exacerbated by the lack of a common and open platform for data entry and management.**

In recent years, the grassroots [SPI-Birds Network & Database](#) has been harmonising data from long-term **Studies of Populations of Individually-marked breeding birds** and facilitating scientific collaboration ([Culina et al. 2021, J. Anim. Ecol.](#)). In its original conception, SPI-Birds provided a community-defined metadata hub and data standard, enabling data integration into larger, synthetic analyses (e.g., [Vriend et al. 2023, Ecology](#)). Practically, data standardisation is accomplished through time-intensive creation of bespoke R pipelines, which programmatically convert highly-individualised datasets into our [Standard Protocol](#) of interacting tables (“process” in Fig. 1). The SPI-Birds Network is growing and currently comprises 137 studies of 45 species in 31 countries. Recently, as part of a two-year CHIST-ERA Open Research Data & Software project (*FAIRBiRDS*; “store” + “share” in Fig. 1), we have been developing a centralised data repository for storing contributed data, a relational database for housing SPI-Birds standard data, and an interface for managing data requests. We have also been curating an open library of standardised codes for working with the SPI-Birds standard data as part of an NWO Open Science Fund project (*CoreBirds*; “analyse” in Fig. 1). Unaddressed by these efforts is the lack of a common data entry platform for breeding bird data (“organise” in Fig. 1), be they SPI-Birds or otherwise. **In the *SPI-BirDES* project, we aim to build on our recent successes to develop an open, modular, and extendable data entry software (DES)** (Fig. 2).

Our proposal is strongly aligned with the specific aims of the Open Science Infrastructure call. The development of a centralised DES will facilitate the continued growth of SPI-Birds as an organisation, complementing our existing and in-development research support infrastructure. **Open infrastructure** | *SPI-BirDES* will facilitate open and FAIR practices by filling a gap in our existing research infrastructure. The software will be freely available as both web-based and desktop applications; source code will be hosted and maintained on GitHub after the project’s completion. *SPI-BirDES* will provide critical infrastructure, not just for SPI-Birds but the wider community of long-term data collectors. **FAIR research practices** | Many researchers seek to adopt better data management practices but lack expertise and financial resources; others rely on front-end software that has reached obsolescence. *SPI-BirDES* will address major vulnerabilities in current data management practices (e.g., data entry in spreadsheets), increase data quality (e.g., error detection), ensure more robust future data curation (e.g., relational database principles), and, in connection with our other infrastructure, enhance the findability and reusability of contributed data. **Empowering and connecting communities** | *SPI-BirDES* will reduce barriers in the FAIR data life cycle and we anticipate doing so will incentivize full participation in the Network, including open data sharing. The modular, extendable nature of the platform will allow researchers to manage any number of other data types not currently part of the SPI-Birds Standard Protocol, and link to their existing data management infrastructure (e.g., in-house databases). *SPI-BirDES* will enable users to directly receive inputted data in the SPI-Birds format, encouraging its adoption, and make it easy to securely deposit data in our repository. We will aggregate study-level metadata through our online repository and search tool, but users will always retain control over their data and the decision to share them with SPI-Birds. Finally, *SPI-BirDES* will further empower researchers by enabling data integration and reducing data heterogeneity.

3.2 Project plan

To achieve our project objectives and to ensure we build a platform that will be adopted by our diverse community of data contributors and data users, we will undertake several activities:

1. **Consultation** | Prior to the start date (Jul 2026), we will host a series of online forums to gauge the interests and data entry needs of the community. These consultations follow our ongoing discussions with a number of SPI-Birds contributors who have expressed interest in joining forces to develop the platform we are proposing (e.g., due to impending obsolescence of current tools or the lack of any stable data entry solution). We will also solicit input through existing channels, such as the SPI-Birds advisory board, newsletter, and mailing list.
2. **Recruitment** | The specific technical aspects related to the *SPI-BirDES* will require the subject expertise of software engineers. We intend to incorporate the eScience Center as a project partner in our full proposal (preferred) or, alternatively, hire a full-time software engineer (or, likely, multiple part-time) (see section 4).
3. **Technology review** | The first month of the project will involve extensive fact finding, in collaboration with recruited personnel, to identify software components that can be adapted, opportunities/challenges related to integration with other data management tools (e.g., institutional databases), web hosting solutions, etc.
4. **Platform development** | The bulk of the project timeline will be devoted to the actual development of the DES. We will follow the agile working method commonly used in software development. By the midpoint of the project, we aim to have a fully-functioning alpha version of the platform.
5. **Beta testing** | We will partner with the SPI-Birds contributors mentioned above to undertake extensive testing of the functionality, user interface, and local deployment of the DES.
6. **Promotion** | We will use a number of avenues to communicate about the DES we develop (see section 4).
7. **Long-term sustainability** | As the host institution for the SPI-Birds core team, NIOO-KNAW will be responsible for the long-term maintenance and hosting of SPI-Birds infrastructure, including the proposed DES.

Figure 2 | mock-up of the proposed modular and extendable DES, including the minimum modules for entry of SPI-Birds standard data and export to contributor-specific formats

3.3 Team composition

The project team comprises the core team of the SPI-Birds Network & Database, hosted at the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW). **JBB** is a Tenure-Track Researcher at NIOO-KNAW focussed on animal responses to environmental change. He has expertise in research data management, curation, and data rescue, and is an inaugural member of the Open Science NL FAIR Data advisory panel. His recent work includes a postdoc with the Canadian Institute of Ecology and Evolution's *Living Data Project*, which aims to preserve environmental data at risk of loss. **SJGV** is Coordinator Veluwe for the *LTER-LIFE* large-scale

research infrastructure aimed at developing digital twins of ecosystems. As the primary developer and data manager for SPI-Birds, he is well-versed in technical aspects of data standardisation, with expertise in FAIR data management practices, metadata standardisation, and reproducible workflows for generating interoperable data. **AČ** is a Senior Researcher at the Ruđer Bošković Institute (Croatia), an Honorary Fellow at NIOO-KNAW, and a pioneer in open science in ecology. She is co-founder of SPI-Birds and a current or recent board member/advisor for several (inter-) national Open Science initiatives, including Open Science NL, European Open Science Cloud, the Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology & Evolutionary biology (SORTEE), FAIRsFAIR, and Open Knowledge Maps, Research Data Alliance working groups, GO FAIR discovery network, UNESCO Open Science working groups, and the National Software Management Plan in the Netherlands. **MEV** is Head of the Department of Animal Ecology at NIOO-KNAW and a leading evolutionary ecologist working with long-term data from wild birds. He has led the Department's long-term nest box monitoring studies for nearly three decades and is deeply embedded in the landscape of long-term ecological studies in the Netherlands and beyond. He is lead investigator of *LTER-LIFE*, a national coordinator of the Long-Term Ecosystem Research–Netherlands (LTER–NL) network, co-founder of SPI-Birds and the Netherlands Society for Evolutionary Biology (NLSEB), and chair of NIOO-KNAW Committee on Data Management.

We anticipate partnering with **eScience Center** to develop and implement our full project proposal (see section 4).

Section 4 – Budget

Type of costs	Short explanation	Costs
Personnel costs	24-month @ 1.0 FTE position for a research software engineer level 3 (estimated on CAO scale 11.4 per eScience Center job profiles using the NWO salary cost formula; €4.963 per month + employer costs) <u>Note:</u> We anticipate incorporating the eScience Center as a partner in our full proposal, allowing their time to be budgeted as personnel costs and our project to benefit from the expertise and contributions of a team of eScience Center developers working part-time on our project. Alternatively, we will hire a single individual for the duration of the project.	~€195,000
Material costs	Knowledge dissemination including: - promotional (infographics, flyers, etc.), translational services, and targeted advertisements aimed at broadening the SPI-Birds Network of contributors - preparation of a user manual - organisation of three workshops (2 x online, 1 x in-person) for potential users at the end of the project - presentation in at least two conferences (1 x national (e.g., Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting), 1 x international (e.g., European Ornithological Union, Hole-nesting Birds Meeting)), including registration, travel, and accommodations - vendor/booth fees for at least two conferences (in addition to those mentioned above)	~€15,000
Other costs	IT costs – project-specific server for hosting the database/repository and data entry tools we develop; institutional ICT support for integrating our platform and server with NIOO-KNAW's existing infrastructure	~€30,000
Total request from NWO		€ 240,000

Section 5 – Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.